

Consumers' Preference for Reduced Pesticide Use in Conventional Vineyards: A Reference Price-Dependent Discrete Choice Experiment

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Abstract

Reducing the use of plant protection products (PPPs) in agriculture has been one of the main targets of the European Union (EU) since 2009. We use the Mediterranean vineyard sector where alternative innovations are being developed to reduce PPPs use as a case study to investigate consumers' willingness to pay (WTP) for wines produced from reduced pesticide use. Using consumers' reference price-dependent discrete choice experiment, we estimate the WTP for red wines produced from different levels of pesticide reduction with different certifications in a Conditional Logit model. The reference price-dependent choice design allows for the estimation of WTP for consumers facing a wide range of wine prices. The WTP for a one percent pesticide reduction ranges from 1.1-5.8 percent of the average reference price depending on the country and category of consumer.

Keywords: Consumers, Logit, Reference-Price-Dependent-DCE, Willingness-to-Pay, Wine

A problem statement

With the EU grapevine sector being one of the major sectors contributing to the high use of PPPs, it is imperative that the sector find alternative innovations to meet the recommended EU targets. Research efforts are underway to find alternative innovations to meet the EU targets. Since the adoption of the innovations by farmers could require an investment cost, the successful adoption of the alternative innovations is therefore partly dependent on wine consumers' WTP for wines produced from reduced pesticide use. However, wine consumers' perception and WTP for wines from reduced pesticide use are currently unknown.

Research question(s) and objectives

The study seeks to answer the question of consumers' perception and willingness to pay for wines produced from different levels of pesticide reduction using alternative innovations. The main objective is to determine the premium that consumers place on environmentally friendly produced wines, specifically, wines produced from reduced pesticide use in vineyards. The study also unravels the socio-demographic and wine attributes driving consumers' preference and willingness to pay for environmentally friendly wines. This is achieved through a discrete choice experiment based on individually stated market prices. This approach contributes to resolving the anchoring price biases in choice experiments.

Method

The study uses a discrete choice experiment (DCE) to achieve its main objective. DCE has been widely applied in the food sector and the wine sector is no exception [1].

As we aware that the number of attributes has influence on the variance of the errors in DCE [2], we carefully design the DCE to take into account all relevant wine attributes without including all them in the design. Three attributes with four levels each as shown in table 1 were used in the DCE.

We used red wine for regular home consumption as the main case study. Due to the wide range of red wine prices, it becomes difficult to find a common reference point for all respondents particularly. In order to avoid presenting price levels far below or above the price known by respondents, a two-stage dynamic process linking the price paid by each consumer and the price levels in each choice sets was developed. Thus, in the first stage, we elicited from all respondents their last purchase price (reference) for red wine bought for regular home consumption. In the second stage, eight choice sets each with three alternatives including the ability to opt for the previous purchase (status quo) were presented to all respondents. The combination of the three attributes was done with NGene™ using D-efficient fractional factorial approach [3]. The dynamic percentage variation of the reference price in the discrete choice experiment (second stage) based on the attributes combinations was made possible by the PIPED TEXT feature in the survey tool qualtrics.

The pesticide reduction attribute is defined as the percentage spray volume of pesticide reduced using alternative innovations. The four levels are based on an eco-friendly alternative innovation capable of reducing the spray volume of pesticides by up to 40%.

Finally, a four level certification attribute is included based on current types of certifications for sustainable food products [4, 5].

Table 1. Attributes definition and levels

Attribute	Definition	Base	Level1	Level2	Level3
Pesticide Reduction	The percentage volume of pesticides that is reduced by conventional vineyards growers using alternative innovations.	-10%	-20%	-30%	-40%
Certification	Use labels/logos/stamps to signify compliance with acceptable practices.	No-certification(0)	Independent/Third party certification(1)	Participatory guaranteed certification(2)	EU/National certification(3)
Price	Price variation in percentage based on respondents' stated reference prices in Euros (€) for a 750ml bottle of red wine for regular home consumption.	50%	5%	20%	35%

You indicated that you usually pay 2.55 € for your 750ml bottle of RED wine for regular consumption at home. Which of the alternative conventional red wines below will you purchase for your usual home consumption based on the level of pesticide reduced by farms, certification and price? IMAGINE that these RED wines are from the same BRAND and have the SAME ATTRIBUTES and CHARACTERISTICS as those you usually purchase for regular home consumption.

Purchase scenario 1

Wine 1

- 30% Pesticide reduction
- Independent/Third-party certification

3.83 €

Wine 2

- 20% Pesticide Reduction
- No certification

2.68 €

None of these (I prefer my last purchase)

Fig. 1 Sample of choice sets

Fig. 2 Summary of Method

Data

The study uses primary data collected from five Mediterranean countries (France, Greece, Italy, Portugal and Spain). The respondents were drawn from a panel of consumers through a quota sampling based on country, gender and age. In addition, respondents had to be mainly involved in household wine purchase decision-making and must have purchased wine in the last three months leading to the survey. A total of 5.091 consumers participated in the survey with the country sample as France(1.013), Greece(1.018), Italy(1.021), Portugal(1.021) and Spain(1.018). The data collection took place in January 2023 and lasted for about month. Apart from the choice elicitation, the data captured the socio-demographic characteristics, perception, opinions, information on the previous

wine purchases for regular home consumption as well as the food technology neophobia (Vidigal, et al., 2015). Wine consumers with preference for organic, biodynamic and other sustainably produced wines (non-conventional wines) were separated from consumers with preference for conventional wines in the choice experiment. Further categorization was done by allowing half of respondents to see the demonstration of the alternative innovation developed to reduce pesticide use while the other half does not see the demonstration. In order to test the validity of the survey, a pre-text involving 120 consumers was done to address preliminary survey concerns.

Results

The table 2 below shows the detailed description of the socio-demographic characteristics of the consumers that underlines the results of the discrete choice experiment. As noted the table, two groups of wine consumers are identified: a) conventional consumers (i.e. consumers of wines produced from grapes cultivated by using synthetic pesticides and b) non-conventional consumers (i.e. consumers of organic, biodynamic and other wines produced from grapes that are cultivated without synthetic pesticides). For instance, out of the 1.013 wine consumers sampled in France, 732 were identified as conventional wine consumers while 231 were identified as non-conventional wine consumers. Each of the two groups was sub-categorized into those two groups: i) SEE (i.e. those who see the visual demonstration of how the alternative innovation works in vineyards and ii) NO (i.e. those who do not see the how the alternative innovations works. For instance, out of the 732 conventional wine consumers identified, 367 were introduced to visual demonstrations while 365 did not see the demonstration.

The WTP for a 1% percent pesticide reduction in vineyards estimated from the conditional logit models ranged between 1.9-5.8%, 1.1-4.7%, 1.2-3.9%, 1.4-5.1% and 1.2-3.8% of the average consumer reference price for France, Greece, Italy, Portugal and Spain respectively depending the category of consumers. For instance in Spain, conventional wine consumers were willing to pay up to 1.7% more of their average reference price while non-conventional consumers were willing to pay up to 3.8% of their reference price for conventional wines produced under reduced pesticide use. Results therefore showed significant difference between conventional and non-conventional wine consumers in terms of the average stated references prices and WTP, which justified the presentation of the different choice sets to the two categories. The socio-demographic

characteristics (i.e. gender, age, income, education, place of residence etc.) show similar distribution among the five countries as well as the 2 categories and 2 sub-categories of wine consumers, which provides a good base for comparing the WTP within and across the different categories and subcategories. Table 1 presents the mean, median, and standard deviation of the top 5 wine attributes ranked on an 11-point Likert scale of importance (-5=not important 0=Neutral +5=Very important). The price, taste, geographic designation, brand name and vintage were regarded as important attributes in the choice of wines with high mean ranks among the 13 wine attributes presented to wine consumers.

Table 2. Some factor determining wine choice and WTP

		France		Greece		Italy		Portugal		France	
		Conv.	Non Conv.	Conv.	Non Conv.	Conv.	Non Conv.	Conv.	Non Conv.	Conv.	Non Conv.
PDO, PGI designation	Mean	7.8	7.8	7.5	8.1	8.1	8.9	7.9	7.8	7.9	8.3
	Median	8.0	8.0	8.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	8.5	9.0	8.0	9.0
	SD	2.6	2.8	2.6	2.5	2.6	2.3	2.7	2.7	2.6	2.6
Price	Mean	8.5	8.1	9.3	8.9	8.7	8.3	9.6	8.6	8.8	8.5
	Median	9.0	8.0	10.0	9.0	9.0	9.0	10.0	9.0	9.0	9.0
	SD	2.1	2.2	1.9	2.0	2.0	2.1	1.7	2.2	2.0	2.2
Vintage	Mean	7.3	7.4	6.9	8.2	5.6	6.6	7.3	7.8	7.9	8.0
	Median	8.0	8.0	7.0	8.0	6.0	6.0	7.0	8.0	8.0	8.0
	SD	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.1	2.7	2.7	2.4	2.6	2.3	2.4
Brand name	Mean	7.5	7.5	7.6	8.1	7.7	8.0	8.2	8.1	8.2	8.5
	Median	8.0	8.0	8.0	9.0	8.0	8.0	9.0	8.0	9.0	9.0
	SD	2.4	2.6	2.4	2.3	2.3	2.3	2.2	2.5	2.1	2.1
Taste	Mean	8.7	8.5	9.2	9.3	8.9	9.2	9.1	9.3	9.1	9.0
	Median	9.0	9.0	10.0	10.0	9.0	10.0	9.0	10.0	9.0	9.0
	SD	2.0	2.2	1.8	1.8	2.0	2.0	1.9	1.9	1.9	2.0
N		732	381	772	246	735	286	942	79	841	177

Source: Survey data |Conv.= conventional wine |Non Conv.= non-conventional wine
|SD=standard deviation

Table 3. Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents (Source: Survey data)

Characteristics	Item	France		Greece		Italy		Portugal		Spain											
		Conventi onal wine	Non- Convention al wine	Conventio nal wine	Non- Conventio nal wine	Conventio nal wine	Non- Conventio nal wine	Conventio nal wine	Non- Conventio nal wine	Convention al wine	Non- Convention al wine										
		SEE (%)	NO (%)	SEE (%)	NO (%)																
Gender	Female	48.2	54.0	50.7	51.1	55.6	48.7	51.3	48.9	47.7	47.6	53.2	60.8	52.6	49.5	71.1	48.8	54.0	48.1	47.8	47.1
	Male	51.8	45.8	49.3	48.9	43.9	51.0	48.7	55.1	51.8	51.9	44.8	39.2	47.4	50.1	29.0	51.2	45.8	51.9	51.1	52.9
Age categories	18-24 years	9.1	9.0	13.6	22.0	7.0	8.5	15.1	12.6	9.9	9.2	11.9	7.0	8.5	10.3	15.8	12.2	9.2	8.9	6.7	13.8
	25-34 years	13.4	16.7	22.1	16.3	13.6	12.3	26.9	22.8	9.6	15.7	22.4	20.3	15.1	15.5	26.3	12.2	12.5	16.4	22.2	23.0
	35-44 years	18.5	19.2	16.4	18.4	20.3	20.6	19.3	20.5	16.4	19.2	22.4	22.4	20.0	21.4	13.2	29.3	22.4	19.0	23.3	32.2
	45-54 years	21.3	18.4	20.7	17.0	24.4	22.1	10.9	18.9	23.8	23.0	21.0	20.3	21.2	20.6	18.4	17.1 2	21.2	24.9	16.7	16.1
	>55 years	37.1	36.7	27.1	26.2	34.8	36.4	27.7	25.5	40.3	33.0	22.4	30.1	35.3	32.2	26.3	29.3	34.7	30.8	31.1	14.9
Person in charge purchase decisions	Exclusively the respondent	45.0	41.6	44.3	41.1	49.2	48.5	56.3	46.5	40.6	40.0	46.9	52.5	40.0	37.2	42.1	31.7	44.8	43.7	45.6	44.8

	Mostly the respondent	30.0	29.9	31.4	32.6	29.7	31.9	28.6	35.4	32.1	34.9	35.7	24.5	33.0	32.2	29.0	43.9	34.5	28.2	35.6	34.5
	The respondent and someone else	25.1	28.5	24.3	26.2	21.1	19.6	15.3	18.1	27.4	25.1	17.5	23.1	27.0	30.6	29.0	24.4	20.7	28.2	18.9	20.7
Place of residence	A city of up to 50,000 residents	65.7	70.4	60.0	63.1	21.7	26.4	24.4	26.8	50.7	53.8	42.0	39.9	43.7	52.1	52.6	53.7	35.2	37.1	35.6	43.7
	A city of between 50,000 to 100,000 residents	17.2	15.6	15.7	19.2	26.7	21.4	28.6	26.0	17.8	16.8	25.9	30.8	24.1	20.4	15.8	24.4	19.8	20.0	27.8	18.4
	A city of more than 100,000 residents	17.2	14.0	24.3	17.7	50.5	50.3	47.1	47.2	31.5	29.5	32.2	29.4	32.2	27.6	31.6	22.0	45.1	43.0	36.7	37.9
Education level	Up to secondary	8.7	8.2	5.7	5.7	30.8	23.6	20.2	19.7	10.7	$\frac{12.1}{6}$	5.6	7.7	10.7	11.8	15.8	9.8	19.3	23.9	31.1	10.3
	Post-secondary	45.2	43.6	37.1	34.0	17.4	19.1	20.2	26.0	55.9	54.1	49.0	48.3	41.9	38.7	26.3	39.0	32.5	27.9	20.0	18.4
	University (Bachelor)	31.6	34.8	41.4	41.8	37.7	40.0	44.5	37.8	23.0	19.2	25.2	25.9	34.0	34.1	34.2	34.2	28.4	28.6	28.9	46.0

	University post graduate. (BSc/Master/PhD)	14.4	13.4	15.7	18.4	14.2	17.3	15.1	16.5	10.4	14.6	20.3	18.2	13.4	15.3	23.7	17.1	19.8	19.5	20.0	25.3
Respondent's level of knowledge on pesticides use in vineyards	No knowledge	39.0	41.6	24.3	26.2	33.2	32.4	21.0	15.8	25.8	28.1	11.2	14.7	37.3	37.2	18.4	29.3	38.8	38.5	14.4	17.2
	Low level	45.2	43.8	47.9	44.7	40.6	42.0	40.3	43.3	54.8	48.7	44.8	48.3	46.6	45.7	42.1	39.0	42.4	44.1	50.0	44.8
	Medium level	12.5	11.8	24.3	24.1	19.5	20.4	25.2	32.3	18.4	19.5	34.3	28.7	14.6	15.8	31.6	26.6	15.7	15.3	25.6	33.3
	High level	3.3	2.7	3.6	4.96	6.7	5.3	13.5	8.7	1.1	3.8	9.8	8.4	1.4	1.3	7.9	4.9	3.1	2.1	10.0	4.6
Net monthly household income	< 1.000 €	9.8	8.8	10.7	7.8	42.0	41.7	40.0	39.4	19.5	17.0	12.6	13.3	43.5	41.6	36.8	48.8	17.6	20.9	11.1	11.5
	1.000-2.000 €	36.5	35.6	27.9	36.2	40.9	40.5	36.1	32.3	50.4	48.7	39.9	44.8	41.0	41.1	36.8	31.7	47.5	43.7	38.9	37.9
	2.001-3.000 €	24.0	27.4	32.1	28.4	10.4	10.3	9.2	8.7	18.9	20.3	24.5	19.6	11.1	11.8	13.2	14.6	23.1	22.3	28.9	27.6
	3.001-4.000 €	14.4	12.3	15.7	13.5	1.3	3.5	2.5	4.7	4.7	5.1	8.4	7.0	1.65	2.6	5.3	2.4	6.5	5.6	8.9	8.1
	4.001-5.000 €	7.6	8.5	5.0	3.6	2.1	1.3	1.7	4.7	3.3	4.6	5.6	6.3	1.4	0.7	2.6	0.0	2.2	4.7	4.4	4.6
	> 5.000 €	7.62	7.4	8.6	10.6	3.2	2.8	8.4	10.2	3.3	4.3	9.1	9.1	1.2	2.2	5.3	2.4	3.1	2.8	7.8	10.4
Sub-total		367	365	140	141	374	398	119	127	365	370	143	143	485	457	38	41	415	426	90	87
TOTAL		1013				1018				1021				1021				1018			

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